

Release of Phosphate from Minerals by Some Chelating Agents

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The phosphate release from vivianite and wavellite by water is practically nil. But aluminon, oxine and cupferron can release phosphate in appreciable amounts from these minerals. The efficiency of phosphate release by these chelating agents used is of the order: aluminon > oxine > cupferron for wavellite and cupferron > oxine > aluminon for vivianite. Such phosphate release from these minerals is possible due to decomposition of mineral structures.

ACID soils often contain different minerals of iron and aluminium phosphate. Dyal¹ identified wavellite in the sand, silt and clay fractions of a soil from Florida. Vivianite (ferrous phosphate), $\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is often present in soils of poor drainage. Stelly and Pierre² found in their experiments that aluminium phosphate minerals variscite and wavellite show lowest solubility in the pH range 4.5-7.0 and iron phosphate minerals dufrenite ($\text{FePO}_4 \cdot \text{Fe}(\text{OH})_3$) and vivianite in the pH ranges 3.0-6.0 and 6.0-7.0 respectively. These minerals, i.e. wavellite and vivianite are usually inactive and remain unchanged during the process of phosphate release by acid soils, so that any device for releasing phosphate from them will definitely increase phosphate availability to plants. In the present paper effect of chelating agents like aluminon, oxine and cupferron on phosphate release from these phosphate minerals was studied.

Experimental

1 g finely powdered samples of vivianite and wavellite were treated with 0.1 gm aluminon, oxine and cup-

ferron, and 50 ml distilled water in different stoppered bottles and the initial pH values of the systems were recorded. Then pH of all these mixtures was maintained at 5.0 by using 0.02 N HCl or NaOH. The systems were treated with a few drops of toluene in order to check fungus growth and left for 7 days with occasional shaking. After this period the final pH values were observed, the mixtures were filtered; from the filtrates, organic matter was decomposed by H_2O_2 and HNO_3 treatment, excess H_2O_2 being decomposed by boiling. The phosphate in these solutions was then determined colorimetrically by the vanadomolybdate method³. Blank estimations of 1 g minerals and 50 ml water kept for 7 days and adjusted initially at pH 5.0 were also performed. Correction of phosphate in H_2O_2 was also made.

The composition of the minerals is tabulated in Table 1 and the results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION OF MINERALS

Material used	Composition
(a) Wavellite as $\text{Al}_2(\text{PO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Al_2O_3 - 35.89%, P_2O_5 - 34.16% H_2O - 28.46%, remaining F & Al = 1.39%
(b) Vivianite as $2[\text{Fe}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	Fe_2O_3 - 9.43%, P_2O_5 - 29.99% SiO_2 - 0.12%, H_2O - 27.70% CaO - 0.02%, MnO - 0.25% FeO - 32.64%

TABLE 2—RELEASE OF PHOSPHATE BY CHELATING AGENTS FROM WAVELLITE AND VIVIANITE

Minerals used	Reagent used to release phosphate	pH			P-release in g/g of minerals
		initial	adjusted	final	
I. Wavellite	(a) by water (control)	6.70	5.0	5.70	nil
	(b) ,, aluminon	6.25	5.0	5.55	2.6×10^{-3}
	(c) ,, oxine	5.20	5.0	5.45	1.2×10^{-3}
	(d) ,, cupferron	6.85	5.0	7.05	0.83×10^{-3}
II. Vivianite	(a) by water (control)	6.00	5.0	5.20	nil
	(b) ,, aluminon	6.10	5.0	5.55	0.25×10^{-3}
	(c) ,, oxine	4.40	5.0	5.00	1.55×10^{-3}
	(d) ,, cupferron	7.65	5.0	7.65	2.0×10^{-3}

Results and Discussions

The results show that :

(i) the pHs of the mineral-chelating agent mixtures have the tendency to revert to their original values,

(ii) release of phosphate from wavellite and vivianite by water is practically nil, and

(iii) when complexing agents are used, the release is enhanced.

The efficiency of phosphate release by the chelating agents used is of the order :

aluminon > oxine > cupferron for wavellite, and
cupferron > oxine > aluminon for vivianite.

The higher phosphate release by aluminon from wavellite is probably due to its better complexing power with Al^{3+} and also due to its higher solubility in water. The higher phosphate release by cupferron from vivianite is probably due to its better complexing power with iron.

In the release process, since pH is increased it is probable that hydroxyl groups present in the minerals are removed i.e. the mineral structure gradually breaks down and replacement of both phosphate and hydroxyl groups for ligands takes place and ultimately the inner metallic complexes $Al L_3$ and $Fe L_3$ are formed (L = chelating group of cupferron, aluminon, oxine).

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